

Neem the Wonder Herb: A Short Review

Rudra Prasad Giri¹, Dr. Ajit. K. Gangawane², Dr. Sucheta Ghorai Giri³

¹Clinical Research Manager, ²Deputy registrar Academic, ³Assistant Professor
¹Clinical Pharmacology Unit, Sun Pharmaceutical Industries Ltd. Vadodara, Gujarat, India

²Parul University, Vadodara, Gujarat, India

³Parul Institute of Applied Sciences, Parul University, Vadodara, Gujarat, India

How to cite this paper: Rudra Prasad Giri | Dr. Ajit. K. Gangawane | Dr. Sucheta Ghorai Giri "Neem the Wonder Herb: A Short Review" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-3, April 2019, pp.962-967, URL: <https://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd23038.pdf>

IJTSRD23038

ABSTRACT

Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) has much importance. Usefulness of neem has already mentioned in several literature. Ayurveda has mentioned its use in many disease conditions. Now public awareness for herbal products are increasing highly so it has been found demand of neem products are increasing day by day. Neem is a plant who's every parts holds multiple usage. Researcher has reported many medicinal benefits of neem. Neem is known for its anti diabetic, anti-inflammatory, anti cancer effect. Neem is used in many hindu rituals. This review work represents several usage of neem which will provide a great knowledge to people and let them know about the wonder of neem.

KEYWORDS: *Neem, Ayurveda, Herbal Medicin, anti-inflammatory, anti cancer*

Copyright © 2019 by author(s) and International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development Journal. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0) (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>)

A. INTRODUCTION:

The neem tree (*Azadirachta indica*) has been perceived as having incredible health promoting properties for centuries. Truth be told, there is proof that up to 4,500 years prior, neem was at that point being utilized to support healing. Its utilization began in ancient India and neighboring nations, where it has for quite some time been worshipped as a standout amongst the most versatile plants known. Indeed, even today, the neem tree is regarded as the "Village Dispensary"—all aspects of it known to have special helpful therapeutic value. The neem tree has a place with the family meliaceae—the mahogany family—and is a fast-growing, evergreen tree surely understood for its drought resistance. The neem tree develops into a substantial shade tree with a thick, round canopy and can live for 150-200 years. And keeping in mind that neem is infamous for its solid unsavory smell, its blossoms have a delectable nectar like aroma that can be smelled for miles. As a fast developing tree that needs little water, neem is likewise an entirely inexhaustible resource.

In Ayurveda, neem is normally used to adjust pitta and kapha. Its cold, light, and dry characteristics will in general aggravate vata. Neem is in this manner regularly prescribed in mix with different herbs that assistance stifle its vata-inciting nature.

B. Benefits of Neem :

Antioxidant Activity: Free radical or receptive oxygen species are one of the fundamental offenders in the genesis of different illnesses. Notwithstanding, neutralization of free radical activity is one of the imperative strides in the maladies counteractive action. Antioxidants stabilize/deactivate free radicals, regularly before they assault focuses in biological cells [1] and furthermore assume job in the activation of anti oxidative protein that assumes job in the control of harm brought about by free radicals/receptive oxygen species. Therapeutic plants have been accounted for to have antioxidant activity [2]. Plants natural products, seeds, oil, leaves, bark, and roots demonstrate an essential job in illnesses aversion because of the rich source of antioxidant. Leaf and bark concentrates of *A. indica* have been considered for their antioxidant activity and aftereffects of the examination plainly shown that leaf and bark extracts/fractions of neem developed in the lower regions have significant antioxidant properties [3]. Another critical examination was performed dependent on leaves, fruits, flowers, and stem bark extracts from the Siamese neem tree to evaluate the antioxidant activity and results recommend that extricates from leaf, blossom, and stem bark have strong antioxidant potential [4].

Anti cancerous Activity: Malignant growth is multi-factorial malady and significant medical issue around the world. The

modification of molecular/genetic pathways assumes job in the improvement and movement of malignant growth. The treatment module dependent on allopathic is compelling on one side yet in addition indicates adverse effect on the typical cell. Prior investigations detailed that plants and their constituents show inhibitory consequences for the development of malignant cells via modulation of cell expansion, apoptosis, tumour suppressor gene and different other molecular pathways [5]. Neem contains flavanoids and different other ingredients that play an essential job in restraint of malignant growth advancement. Extensive number of epidemiological examinations suggests that high flavonoid admission might be related with a diminished danger of malignancy [6].

Anti-Inflammatory Effect of Neem: Plants or their isolated derivatives are in the practice to treat/act as anti-inflammatory agents. An examination result has affirmed that concentrate of *A. indica* leaves at a dose of 200mg/kg, p. o., demonstrated huge anti-inflammatory activity in cotton pellet granuloma test in rodents [7]. Other examination results uncovered that neem leaf extricates demonstrated significant anti-inflammatory impact yet it is less effective than that of dexamethasone [8] and examine results propose that nimbidin stifles the elements of macrophages and neutrophils pertinent to inflammation [9]. Prior finding demonstrated immune modulator and anti-inflammatory impact of bark and leave concentrates and antipyretic and anti-inflammatory exercises of oil seeds [10, 11]. Experimentation was made to assess the pain relieving action of neem seed oil on albino rats and after effects of the examination demonstrated that neem seed oil indicated huge pain relieving impact in the portion of 1 and 2 mL/kg and oil has dose-dependent pain relieving action [12]. Another examination was made to explore the anti-inflammatory impact of neem seed oil (NSO) on albino rats utilizing carrageen an-incited rear paw edema and results uncovered that NSO indicated expanded hindrance of paw edema with the dynamic increment in dose from 0.25mL to 2 mL/kg body weight. At the portion of 2 mL/kg body weight, NSO demonstrated most extreme (53.14%) hindrance of edema at fourth hour of carrageen an injection [13].

Hepatoprotective Effect: Therapeutic plants and their ingredients play a significant activity as hepatoprotective with no antagonistic ensnarement's. An examination was performed to inquire about the hepatoprotective employment of azadirachtin-An in carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄) impelled hepatotoxicity in rodents and histology and ultrastructure results certified that pretreatment with azadirachtin-A dose dependently diminished hepatocellular corruption [14]. Other than after-effects of the examination exhibit that pretreatment with azadirachtin-An at the higher dose levels bearably restores the rat liver to normal [14].

Wound Healing Effect: Different plants/their constituents accept a basic occupation in the damage recovering effect. An examination was made to evaluate the damage patching activity of the concentrates of leaves of *A. indica* and *T. cordifolia* using extraction and cut injury models in Sprague Dawley rodents and results revealed that concentrate of the two plants basically propelled the damage mending activity in both extraction and entry point damage models [16]. In addition, in section point wound, rigidity of the recuperating tissue of the two plants treated group was seen to be significantly higher when appeared differently in relation to

the control groups [15]. Distinctive results showed that leave concentrates of *Azadirachta indica* advance damage retouching activity through expanded provocative reaction neovascularization [17]. An examination was grasped to evaluate the 70% alcoholic neem root bark remove (NRE) in diabetes and results showed that neem root bark extricate gave measurably noteworthy results in 800mg/kg portion [18]. Another examination was performed to take a look at the pharmacological hypoglycemic action of *Azadirachta indica* in diabetic rodents and results exhibited that in a glucose versatility test with neem extricate 250mg/kg indicated glucose levels were fundamentally less when contrasted and the control group and *Azadirachta indica* basically decline glucose levels at fifteenth day in diabetic rodents [19].

Antibacterial Activity: An examination was performed to survey antimicrobial sufficiency of home grown choices as endodontic irrigants and differentiated and the standard irrigant sodium hypochlorite and result confirmed that leaf concentrates and grape seed extricates demonstrated zones of restriction prescribing that they had antimicrobial properties [20]. Moreover, leaf extract showed fundamentally more remarkable zones of inhibition than 3% sodium hypochlorite [20]. The antibacterial development of guava and neem isolates against 21 strains of food borne pathogens was evaluated and delayed consequence of the examination recommended that guava and neem extracts have compounds containing antibacterial properties that can possibly be significant to control food borne pathogens and deterioration life forms [21].

Antiviral Activity: Results exhibited that neem bark (NBE) remove basically blocked HSV-1 entry into cells at obsessions stretching out from 50 to 100 µg/mL [22]. Furthermore, blocking development of NBE was seen when the concentrate was preincubated with the disease anyway not with the objective cells proposing a quick enemy of HSV-1 property of the neem bark [23]. Leaves concentrate of neem (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss.) (NCL-11) has shown virucidal development against coxsackievirus contamination B-4 as proposed by methods for disease inactivation and yield decline look at other than interfering at an early event of its replication cycle [24].

Antifungal Activity: Investigation was made to assess the adequacy of different concentrates of neem leaf on seed borne parasites *Aspergillus* and *Rhizopus* and results affirmed that development of both the contagious species was fundamentally repressed and controlled with both alcoholic and water extract. Moreover, alcoholic concentrate of neem leaf was best.

Dentistry: An investigation was made to survey the adequacy of neem dependent on mouth flush with respect to its anti gingivitis impact and concentrate affirmed that *A. indica* mouth flush is similarly viable in diminishing periodontal records as chlorhexidine [25]. Another investigation was completed to assess the antimicrobial properties of natural concentrates of neem against three bacterial strains causing dental caries and results demonstrated that oil ether and chloroform remove indicated solid antimicrobial action against *S. mutans*. Chloroform remove demonstrated solid action against *Streptococcus salivarius* and third strain *Fusobacterium nucleatum* was highly sensitive to both ethanol and water extricate [26]. Prior finding affirmed that dried chewing

sticks of neem indicated most extreme antibacterial action against *S. mutans* when contrasted with *S. salivarius*, *S. mitis*, and *S. sanguis* [27].

Early research recommends that applying a gel containing neem leaf concentrate to the teeth and gums twice day by day for about a month and a half may lessen the measure of plaque on the teeth. It likewise may diminish the quantity of microorganisms in the mouth that can cause plaque. It's indistinct if utilizing a mouth wash containing neem diminishes plaque. Some exploration demonstrates that utilizing a neem mouth flush is helpful, however other research demonstrates no ben.

Antinephrotoxicity Effect: A trial was made to explore the impacts of methanolic leaves extract of *Azadirachta indica* (MLEN) on cisplatin-(CP-) actuated nephrotoxicity and oxidative stress in rodents and results affirmed that extricate adequately saves the kidney from CP-interceded oxidative damage [22]. Moreover, PCR results for caspase-3 and caspase-9 and Bax qualities indicated down regulation in MLEN treated groups [28].

Neuroprotective Effects: An examination was performed to explore the neuroprotective impacts of *Azadirachta indica* leaves against cisplatin-(CP-) prompted neurotoxicity and results demonstrated that morphological discoveries of neem when CP infusion inferred an all around saved brain tissue. No changes, in biochemical parameters, were seen with neem treated groups [29].

Potential Contraceptive Properties of Neem: Utilization of Neem as either a pre or post coital contraceptive, taking note of that it averted expansion of sperm cells in fixations as low as 0.05 to 1%. Filtered concentrates of Neem contained immune modulators that animate the cells and macrophages that end pregnancies. Fertility was recovered after a couple of cycles with no evident effect to future pregnancies.

Immuno stimulatory Compound: Immuno invigorating properties of neem is most critical advantage. It helps both the lymphocytic and cell-intervened frameworks, including "Killer T" cells which can obliterate organisms, infections and malignancy cells by infusing poisonous synthetic compounds into the intruders.

Sexually Transmitted Diseases: Neem demonstrates extraordinary potential to control explicitly transmitted maladies. Neem gave 75% security from the HIV infection.

Stress: Low doses of Neem leaf extricates have sedative impacts. The impact vanishes at high doses, roughly 400 or 800 milligrams for each kilograms of body weight. It additionally lessens tension and stress.

Ulcers: Utilizing Neem bark diminishes 77% gastric corrosive emission just as gastric discharge volume 63% and pepsin movement 50%, because of its anti-inflammatory ingredients, gastric harm is decreased.

Arthritis: Neem has a long history of relieving inflamed joints. Neem helps in diminishing aggravation as well as smother the agony. It is likewise valuable in Rheumatism.

Heart Disease: Significant reasons for a heart attack incorporate blood clumps, elevated cholesterol, arrhythmic heart activity and hypertension. Its leaf removes have

diminished coagulating, brought down circulatory strain and awful cholesterol, impeded fast or strangely high heartbeat and repressed sporadic heart rhythms.

Skin and Blood: Neem is well known and celebrated for rejuvenating skin and a reasonable appearance. Due to a limited extent to its severe taste, it has an unfathomably cooling impact on the body, diminishing overabundance heat that can show as skin imperfections.

Immune System: Its detoxifying impacts on the body make it an incredible invulnerable supporter, particularly for the purifying of ama from the body.

GI Tract: A healthy stomach related condition is essential for wellbeing. Neem decreases undesirable warmth and toxins in the GI tract.

Metabolism: Neem's skapha-lessening properties empower legitimate fat and water processing and end, keeping water maintenance from accumulating in the body.

Lungs: Neem underpins clear breathing and a sound respiratory framework.

Skin Moisture and Softness: Neem's skin benefits work both inside and externally. As an outer application, Neem oil or cleanser mitigates and grease up the skin.

Hair: For those with overabundance pitta and warmth caught in the scalp and hair follicles, neem is tremendous for cooling the scalp and supporting the development of shiny, smooth hair.

Insect repellent: Early research demonstrates that applying concentrate of neem root or leaf to the skin repulses black flies. Likewise, applying neem oil cream to the skin appears to secure against certain kinds of mosquitos.

Psoriasis: Early research proposes that taking neem extricate by mouth for 12 weeks, alongside day by day sun presentation and the utilization of a coal tar and salicylic acid cream, may make the side effects of psoriasis less serious.

Malaria: Jungle fever (Malaria) is very basic in India and all through the tropics. Neem leaf extricates forestalls typical advancement of the jungle fever (Malaria) infection. Despite the fact that Neem might be successful against skin inflammation and other relentless conditions. Psoriasis is effectively treated with Neem oil.

Vitiligo: Vitiligo is accepted to be an immune system issue that makes patches of skin lose its shading. The dosage is of four grams of Neem leaves three times a day, ideally taken before each meal. Neem oil applied to the affected areas could aid in the reversal of discoloration.

Viral Diseases: In India, Neem is likewise used to treat viral infections, for example, smallpox, chicken-pox. Neem has antibacterial qualities also.

AIDS: The absolute best news is that Neem may help in the scan for anticipation or a remedy for AIDS. AIDS may perhaps be treated by ingesting Neem leaf separates or the entire leaf or by drinking a Neem tea.

Neem in Ayurveda: Neem is very unpleasant in taste, which gives it a ground-breaking cooling vitality (virya). This

cooling principle, joined with its ability to help healthy blood, balances pitta—especially when there is heat in rakta dhatu (the blood). Excess pitta can show in various ways; one unmistakable area is the skin. Neem glues and oils have customarily been connected to the skin as a methods for mitigating and greasing up it, quieting aggravated and warmed sensations, keeping up agreeable body temperature, and supporting healthy skin and nails. Neem's light and dry characteristics enable it to counter kapha also. Neem supports healthy assimilation and arouses meda dhatu agni (the metabolic/stomach related rule inside fat tissue), empowering appropriate digestion, and supporting glucose levels that are now in the typical range. Usually taken inside to encourage a condition of parity in the liver, pancreas, and stomach related tract. Neem's bitterness likewise improves taste, which is at the foundation of sound digestion. Neem has a comparable adjusting impact on pitta and kapha in prana vaha srotas (the respiratory sections). On a more extensive scale, neem bolsters normal purifying of the directs in the body just as the revival of solid tissues. Because neem is vata irritating without anyone else, it is joined with different herbs relying upon the ideal impact.

Association with Hindu festivals in India: Neem leaf or bark is viewed as a compelling pitta pacifier as a result of its unpleasant taste. Consequently, it is customarily suggested amid late-spring in Ayurveda (that is, the month of Chaitra according to the Hindu Calendar which for the most part falls in the period of March – April).

In the Indian conditions of Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka and Telangana, Neem blossoms are prominent for their utilization in 'Ugadi Pachhadi' (soup-like pickle), which is made on Ugadi day. In Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, and Telangana, a little measure of Neem and Jaggery (Bevu-Bella) is expended on Ugadi day, the Telugu and Kannada new year, demonstrating that one should take both harsh and sweet things throughout everyday life, joy and sorrow.

Amid Gudi Padva, which is the New Year in the province of Maharashtra, the old routine with regards to drinking a little amount of neem juice or paste on that, prior day beginning celebrations, is found. As in numerous Hindu celebrations and their relationship with some sustenance to maintain a strategic distance from adverse reactions of the period or change of seasons, neem juice is related with Gudi Padva to remind individuals to utilize it amid that specific month or season to appease summer pitta.

In Tamil Nadu amid the late spring a very long time of April to June, the Mariamman temple celebration is a thousand-year-old convention. The Neem leaves and blossoms are the most vital piece of the Mariamman celebration. The statue of the goddess Mariamman will be garlanded with Neem leaves and blossoms. Amid most events of festivities and weddings the general population of Tamil Nadu embellish their surroundings with the Neem leaves and blossoms as a type of adornment and furthermore to avoid evil spirits and diseases.

In the eastern coastal territory of Odisha the renowned Jagannath temple divinities are comprised of Neem heart wood alongside some other basic oils and powders.

C. Different Parts of Neem in use:

Flowers: Most pieces of the neem tree are dreadfully unpleasant, except for its blossoms. White and sensitive,

neem blooms with their grayish buds are too lovely to even consider being eaten and inconceivably restorative. The blossoms have a sweet, practically supernatural jasmine like aroma during the evening and bloom once toward the evening and afterward again at night. Amid the rainstorm, you'll see a group of them dissipated appropriate under the tree. Otherwise called Vepampoo in Tamil, these neem blossoms can be utilized new, dried or in a powdered form. They're utilized usually in the South to cook various dishes: bloom rice, pachadi, rasam, lentils and that's just the beginning. They're frequently dry simmered and sprinkled over the dish to embellish also. Neem blossoms can be utilized to treat anorexia, nausea, belching and intestinal worms.

Leaves: Neem leaves have superb restorative properties. Notwithstanding it's convenience in Pest the executives and Disease control they can likewise be sustained to animals when blended with other grain. Neem leaves are utilized in certain pieces of Indian as manure in rice fields, particularly in the south Indian states. In certain nations, Neem leaves are utilized as mulch in tobacco and tomato fields. They can be all around viably used to execute weeds by spreading them over plant roots to hold dampness. Neem leaves can likewise be utilized to protect stored woolen and silk garments from creepy crawlies.

Neem Cake: Neem cake is versatile and has numerous usage. It very well may be utilized as animals feed, compost and regular pesticide. It gives natural nitrogen as well as hinders the nitrification procedure, when blended with urea, before applying in the fields. Such utilization of the neem covered urea in 90:10 extent can spare upto 30% of the all out synthetic nitrogen prerequisite of the harvests which generally would go waste. This outcomes in cost decreases of horticultural production. Neem cake is generally utilized in India as compost for sugarcane, vegetable and other money crops.

Fruits: Neem fruits are unpleasant, laxative, antihemorrhoidal and anthelmintic (vermifuge) in nature.

Twigs & Bark: If you were born in India, you would have seen individuals bite away at a neem twig. For a long time now, a neem twig is the thing that individuals utilized as a make-do toothbrush. It kills germs, keeps up the soluble dimensions in your salivation, keeps microscopic organisms under control, treats swollen gums and furthermore gives you more white teeth. The twig additionally shreds into strings, practically like fibers that likewise wreck and forestall plaque.

Neem Oil: Neem oil that is separated from neem seeds is wealthy in therapeutic properties which are what makes it an incredible compound in beautifying agents and other excellent items: cleansers, hair oil, hand wash, cleanser and so on. It can treat a large no of skin sicknesses and is known to be an incredible mosquito repellent. Neem can be blended with coconut oil and apply it over your body too. It is trusted that in India, little kids are encouraged neem oil as a sort of fix all. Other than being such an incredible Ayurvedic healer, neem oil can be utilized to ensure different plants. It can likewise be utilized in creams, cleansers and other restorative items.

D. The Future scope:

Medicines: Herbal remedies are utilized for treatment of various kinds of maladies in all pieces of world. Neem tree is

an essential piece of these herbal drugs and is referenced in numerous old writings managing meds. Customary Indian medicinal specialists place it at the zenith of their pharmacopeia. Because of uncommon properties of Neem, its bark, leaves, blossoms, seed and natural product mash were and are currently used to treat a wide scope of sicknesses and grumblings running from disease, diabetes, ulcers to skin issue and stoppage and so forth. Researchers from the created world are working widely in investigating Neem tree and its properties to define new anti-infection agents.

Beautifying agents: Different pieces of Neem tree are being utilized widely in assembling of cleansers, skin creams/salves, shampoos, toothpastes, magnificence helps and toiletries. The Neem twigs are all the more generally being utilized as germicide tooth brushes. As a rule Neem oil/extricate is being utilized for making these beauty care products like cleansers and tooth pastes and so on.

Agricultural: It is in horticulture where the majority of the researchers centered their exploration for investigating the advantages of Neem for crop production. In view of those discoveries, Neem oil, Neem cake, leaves and different pieces of Neem tree are being utilized broadly in the farming area in various places of world. Its primary uses in the farming segment incorporate being a bug spray in nourishment stockpiling, as soil change, manure proficiency enhancer, and powerful foliar pesticide.

Food Storage: In every aspect of tropics, a great part of the gathered nourishment is lost amid capacity on account of worms, insects and different invasions. Individuals don't like to utilize synthetics bug sprays on put away grains when all is said in done and all the more explicitly for sustenance put away for their very own utilization. For quite a long time, Neem oil has given ranchers a powerful cure against such bugs. An exceptionally light covering of Neem oil ensures put away harvests for as long as 20 months from a wide range of invasions with no decay or loss of agreeability. Neem new leaves are additionally utilized on little scale for capacity of nourishment grain at home successfully, yet this is being done on a small scale.

Soil Amendment: Neem cake (after the oil is separated from the seed parts, the left over material is called cake) has been utilized for a long time all through Indian sub mainland as a successful soil formation. Ranchers of this area have learned through experience that utilizing Neem cake in soil produces bigger and more beneficial plants that have few or no bug/sickness issue. A few examinations were additionally led by various researchers to discover why plants developed better in soil blended with Neem cake. Their outcomes uncovered that Neem cake is more extravagant in plant accessible supplements than fertilizers; it slaughtered harming nematodes, advanced vast populace of night crawlers, helped keep nitrogen in the dirt accessible for plants and give critical assurance from bugs. Ranchers of that district have a reasonable thought that by slaughtering nematodes in soil, a noteworthy plant bug is disposed of from soil. Nematodes are exceptionally destructive for plants. Nematodes suck juice from foundations of plants to the point where they are unfit to supply adequate supplements to the plant. At that point the plants look unfortunate, neglect to develop and may in the end bite the dust in spite of adequate sustenance, water and care. Utilization of Neem cake in soil additionally enables keep to

soil free by advancing night crawler exercises in soil, which helps in ingestion of supplements and water by plants all the more effectively and proficiently. Neem cake enables plants to build up a solid resistance framework against these nuisance assaults by at first shielding plants from creepy crawly/bother. Besides, Neem mixes consumed through soil upgrade these regular protection frameworks with demonstrated nutritive, antifungal and creepy crawly repellent properties of Neem.

Poverty: The present detonating development in human populace is genuinely exhausting the world's regular stores and monetary assets. Except if the flee human populace development rate is backed off, there would be little trust in raising everybody out of neediness in the creating scene. Other than instructive requirements, the non-accessibility of modest techniques for contraception, which don't cause injury or tasteful, social, and religious sensitivities of individuals, limit the accomplishment of birth guideline programs. In any case, ongoing discoveries show that some Neem subsidiaries may fill in as reasonable and generally accessible contraceptives. An ongoing controlled investigation in the Indian armed force demonstrated the viability of Neem as a prophylactic. As indicated by an ongoing report by the Washington based International Food Policy Research Institute, by 2020, the world will be a considerably more unjustifiable spot than it is at present, with sustenance surpluses in the industrialized world and with constant precariousness and nourishment deficiencies in the south, especially in African nations.

E. Conclusion

Popularity of natural products or their derivatives role in diseases cure and prevention is increasing worldwide due to less side effect properties. Neem and its fixings have therapeutics suggestion and have been customarily utilized worldwide particularly in Indian Subcontinent since old time. Clinical based examinations affirmed that neem assumes essential job in aversion of different maladies. The job of dynamic fixings as chemo preventive impact has been seen in different tumor by means of balance of various cell flagging pathways. The nitty gritty examination ought to be made dependent on creature to know the accurate mechanism of action in the diseases management.

Reference:

- [1] P. X. Nunes, S. F. Silva, R. J. Guedes, and S. Almeida, "Biological oxidations and antioxidant activity of natural products," in *Phytochemicals as Nutraceuticals—Global Approaches to Their Role in Nutrition and Health*, InTech, 2012.
- [2] A. H. Rahmani and S. M. Aly, "Nigella sativa and its active constituents thymoquinone shows pivotal role in the diseases prevention and treatment," *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 48–53, 2015.
- [3] A. K. Ghimeray, C. W. Jin, B. K. Ghimire, and D. H. Cho, "Antioxidant activity and quantitative estimation of azadirachtin and nimbin in *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss grown in foothills of Nepal," *African Journal of Biotechnology*, vol. 8, no. 13, pp. 3084–3091, 2009.
- [4] P. Sithisarn, R. Supabphol, and W. Gritsanapan, "Antioxidant activity of Siamese neem tree (VP 1209)," *Journal of Ethno pharmacology*, vol. 99, no. 1, pp. 109–112, 2005.

- [5] A. H. Rahmani, M. A. Alzohairy, M. A. Khan, and S. M. Aly, "Therapeutic implications of black seed and its constituent thymoquinone in the prevention of cancer through inactivation and activation of molecular pathways," *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, vol. 2014, Article ID 724658, 13 pages, 2014.
- [6] L. Le Marchand, "Cancer preventive effects of flavonoids—a review," *Biomedicine and Pharmacotherapy*, vol. 56, no. 6, pp. 296–301, 2002.
- [7] R. R. Chattopadhyay, "Possible biochemical mode of anti-inflammatory action of *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss. in rats," *Indian Journal of Experimental Biology*, vol. 36, no. 4, pp. 418–420, 1998.
- [8] A. S. M. Mosaddek and M. M. U. Rashid, "A comparative study of the anti-inflammatory effect of aqueous extract of neem leaf and dexamethasone," *Bangladesh Journal of Pharmacology*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 44–47, 2008.
- [9] G. Kaur, M. Sarwar Alam, and M. Athar, "Nimbidin suppresses functions of macrophages and neutrophils: relevance to its anti-inflammatory mechanisms," *Physiotherapy Research*, vol. 18, no. 5, pp. 419–424, 2004.
- [10] N. Arora, A. Koul, and M. P. Bansal, "Chemo preventive activity of *Azadirachta indica* on two-stage skin carcinogenesis in murine model," *Physiotherapy Research*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 408–416, 2011.
- [11] K. Biswas, I. Chattopadhyay, R. K. Banerjee, and U. Bandyopadhyay, "Biological activities and medicinal properties of Neem (*Azadirachta indica*)," *Current Science*, vol. 82, no. 11, pp. 1336–1345, 2002.
- [12] S. Kumar, D. Agrawal, J. Patnaik, and S. Patnaik, "Analgesic effect of neem (*Azadirachta indica*) seed oil on albino rats," *International Journal of Pharma and Bio Sciences*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. P222–P225, 2012.
- [13] M. R. Naik, A. Bhattacharya, R. Behera, D. Agrawal, S. Dehury, and S. Kumar, "Study of anti-inflammatory effect of neem seed oil (*Azadirachta indica*) on infected albino rats," *Journal of Health Research and Reviews*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 66–69, 2014.
- [14] N. S. Baligar, R. H. Aladakatti, M. Ahmed, and M. B. Hiremath, "Hepatoprotective activity of the neem-based constituent azadirachtin-A in carbon tetrachloride intoxicated Wistar rats," *Canadian Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology*, vol. 92, no. 4, pp. 267–277, 2014.
- [15] D. A. Of usori, B. A. Falana, A. E. Ofusori, T. A. Abayomi, S. A. Ajayi, and G. B. Ojo, "Gastro protective effect of aqueous extract of neem *Azadirachta indica* on induced gastric lesion in rats," *International Journal of Biological and Medical Research*, vol. 1, p. 219–222, 2010.
- [16] C. C. Barua, A. Talukdar, A. G. Barua, A. Chakraborty, R. K. Sarma, and R. S. Bora, "Evaluation of the wound healing activity of methanolic extract of *Azadirachta Indica* (Neem) and *Tinospora cordifolia* (Guduchi) in rats," *Pharmacology online*, vol. 1, pp. 70–77, 2010.
- [17] A. Osunwoke Emeka, J. Olotu Emamoke, A. Allison Theodore, and C. Onyekwere Julius, "The wound healing effects of aqueous leave extracts of *azadirachta indica* on wistar rats," *Journal of Natural Science and Research*, vol. 3, no. 6, 2013.
- [18] P. R. Patil, S. P. Patil, A. Mane, and S. Verma, "Antidiabetic activity of alcoholic extract of Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) root bark," *National Journal of Physiology, Pharmacy and Pharmacology*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 142–146, 2013.
- [19] S. K. Dholi, R. Raparla, S. K. Mankala, and K. Nagappan, "Invivo antidiabetic evaluation of Neem leaf extract in alloxan induced rats," *Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 100–105, 2011.
- [20] W. N. Ghonmode, O. D. Balsaraf, V. H. Tambe, K. P. Saujanya, A. K. Patil, and D. D. Kakde, "Comparison of the antibacterial efficiency of neem leaf extracts, grape seed extracts and 3% sodium hypochlorite against *E. faecalis*—an in vitro study," *Journal of International Oral Health*, vol. 5, no. 6, pp. 61–66, 2013.
- [21] M. D. Mahfuzul Hoque, M. L. Bari, Y. Inatsu, V. K. Juneja, and S. Kawamoto, "Antibacterial activity of guava (*Psidium guajava* L.) and neem (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss.) extracts against food borne pathogens and spoilage bacteria," *Food borne Pathogens and Disease*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 481–488, 2007.
- [22] M. B. Yerima, S. M. Jodi, K. Oyinbo, H. M. Maishanu, A. A. Farouq, and A. U. Junaidu, "Effect of neem extracts (*Azadirachta indica*) on bacteria isolated from adult mouth," *Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, vol. 20, pp. 64–67, 2012.
- [23] V. Tiwari, N. A. Darmani, B. Y. J. T. Yue, and D. Shukla, "In vitro antiviral activity of neem (*Azadirachta indica* L.) bark extract against herpes simplex virus type-1 infection," *Physiotherapy Research*, vol. 24, no. 8, pp. 1132–1140, 2010.
- [24] L. Badam, S. P. Joshi, and S. S. Bedekar, "In vitro' antiviral activity of neem (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss) leaf extract against group B coxsackieviruses," *Journal of Communicable Diseases*, vol. 31, no. 2, pp. 79–90, 1999.
- [25] A. Chatterjee, M. Saluja, N. Singh, and A. Kandwal, "To evaluate the antigingivitis and antipalque effect of an *Azadirachta indica* (neem) mouthrinse on plaque induced gingivitis: a double blind, randomized, controlled trial," *Journal of Indian Society of Periodontology*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 398–401, 2011.
- [26] N. C. J. P. Lekshmi, N. Sowmia, S. Viveka, Jr. Brindha, and S. Jeeva, "The inhibiting effect of *Azadirachta indica* against dental pathogens," *Asian Journal of Plant Science and Research*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 6–10, 2012.
- [27] V. R. Chava, S. M. Manjunath, A. V. Rajanikanth, and N. Sridevi, "The efficacy of neem extract on four microorganisms responsible for causing dental caries viz *Streptococcus mutans*, *Streptococcus salivarius*, *Streptococcus mitis* and *Streptococcus sanguis*: an in vitro study," *Journal of Contemporary Dental Practice*, vol. 13, no. 6, pp. 769–772, 2012.
- [28] A. E. Abdel Moneim, M. S. Othman, and A. M. Aref, "*Azadirachta indica* attenuates cisplatin-induced nephrotoxicity and oxidative stress," *Bio Med Research International*, vol. 2014, Article ID 647131, 11 pages, 2014.
- [29] A. E. Abdel Moneim, "*Azadirachta indica* attenuates cisplatin induced neurotoxicity in rats," *Indian Journal of Pharmacology*, vol. 46, no. 3, pp. 316–321, 2014.